

Instrument Timbre Transformation using Gaussian Mixture Models

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Abstract

Timbre is one of the fundamental elements for the identification of a musical instrument and is closely connected with its perceived quality and production type (blown, plucked, etc.). Thus, timbre is heavily responsible for each instrument's character and color and consequently responsible for its perceptual identification. An application that aims to the timbral transformation of one instrument into another, should address the issues of capturing the timbral characteristics of both source and target and converting one into another. This must be carried out in such a way, so that the listener, ideally, should not be able to distinguish a recording of the target instrument from the result of the transformation.

In this thesis, we consider a method that is based on timbre modeling by means of the spectral envelope and using Gaussian mixture models (GMMs) extracts a function for instrument transformation. Our proposed framework is based on prior work and theory on voice conversion and incorporates a Line Spectral Frequencies (LSFs)-based representation of an all-pole model of the spectral envelope to perform transformation of the source instrument envelope into that of the target. We

will be adapting principles from voice conversion, proposing several adjustments, modifications and additions in order to make it meaningful for instrument timbre transformation. The resulting framework which performance we present and evaluate, will be referred to as Instrument Transformation Framework (ITF).

Key words: Instrument Timbre Transformation, Statistical Models, Gaussian Mixture Model, All-Pole, AR models, LSF

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Chapter 1

Introduction

One of the basic elements of sound is color, or timbre. Timbre describes all of the aspects of a musical sound that are not related to a sound's pitch, loudness, or length. In other words, when a flute plays a note, and then an oboe plays the same note, for the same length of time and at the same loudness, one can still easily distinguish between the two sounds, because a flute sounds “different” from an oboe. This difference lies in the timbre of the sounds. Moreover, the human ear and brain are capable of hearing and appreciating very small variations in timbre, enabling us to distinguish between the various types of instruments but also between the differences of instruments of the same type [15]. This work addresses the task of timbre transformation of musical signals in order to achieve instrument transformation, investigating to what extent this direction can provide us with quality results.

As mentioned above, in this thesis we consider a novel approach for the transformation of one musical instrument into another, with respect to their timbral characteristics. Rephrasing, we can describe the objective of this work as to be able to process and transform an audio signal coming from a source instrument X into an audio signal containing the original melodic information but with the timbral characteristics of a predefined target instrument Y. An ultimate goal of such an attempt would be to obtain an audio signal with the original “musical score”, as if it were performed by the target instrument Y, instead of X.

1.1 Scope and orientation

One of the main goals of the present work is to explore to what extent it is possible, combining an all-pole model for the representation of the timbre signal and a technique based on Gaussian mixture models (GMMs), to perform timbral transformation of a source instrument into a target instrument.

The approach consists of a time-continuous transformation based on GMMs containing the spectral envelope information, since timbral information is assumed to be contained in the spectral envelope. This method enables us to have a pre-trained model that can be used in a variety of cases without the need for complicated processing of the signal. The use of GMMs is very common in fields like voice conversion, instrument classification and speech recognition, among many others as presented in [1], [2], [7], [8]. However there has been little work on the application of GMMs for instrument or musical transformation and morphing [4], [5]. As mentioned in [4], GMMs seem appropriate due to their capability to model arbitrary densities and to represent general spectral features.

Another challenging issue that one encounters when dealing with audio analysis and transformation for real time applications is latency. The latency limitations introduced by the traditional analysis chain with windowing and passing to the frequency domain by FFT are hard to resolve or come around. So when considering the problem of instrument transformation and using the traditional techniques, several issues emerge. The use of windows, combined with algorithms for accurate fundamental frequency estimation such as yin [18] inevitably introduce undesirable latency to our system. Given the fact that we need approximately four complete periods of the input signal under our window (depending on the window of choice) [18], it becomes clear that the performance will drop when needing large windows. Analysis with smaller windows performs satisfactory in the high frequency range, but the resolution in the lower band drops dramatically. Our proposed system was tested offline (training and transformation) but is based on a frame-by-frame

processing basis and can be adapted to avoid fundamental frequency detection, replacing it with a faster envelope estimation. The latency advantage has originally served as motivation for following this approach, as its success could have an impact on pitch-to-midi systems, guitar synthesizers, etc. In the timeframe of this thesis it hasn't been possible to confirm the validity of the previous hypothesis, but all the aforementioned theoretical advantages stand and can spawn further research towards that direction.

Initially we had defined our possible instrument space to contain electric guitar, acoustic guitar and one instrument of different family, such as a brass instrument (alto sax). However, studying the specific characteristics within a variety of instruments we concluded in limiting this study to two different types of saxophones, the alto and the soprano saxophone. The motivation for this choice will be addressed later on.

1.2 Outline

The remainder of the thesis is organized as follows: Chapter 2 introduces the basic principles of voice conversion as well as of the GMM theory. These basics of the voice conversion framework are presented as it will serve as the basis for our proposed Instrument Transformation Framework (ITF). Chapter 3 states the basic motivation and justification for the use of GMMs for instrument timbre transformation as well as the preliminary results that guided us towards that direction. Chapter 4 is dedicated to the presentation of the implemented system (ITF). Chapter 5 outlines and comments on the current results and the performance of the ITF. Chapter 6 summarizes and concludes the current work and presents ideas and proposals for future work.

Chapter 2

Voice Conversion and background theory

In this chapter, we present the basic principles of voice conversion (VC). As stated in previous chapters, this thesis addresses the task of instrument timbre conversion and does not deal with voice conversion. However the core and architecture of the ITF is strongly based on previous works on voice conversion as the ones presented in [1] and [2] and thus this chapter is dedicated to an overall presentation of the existing Voice Conversion framework and the basic principles of Gaussian mixture models. Design and implementation characteristics of the VC framework are beyond the scope of this work and are analyzed in detail in [1] and [2].

2.1 Voice conversion principles

There are many elements that define the identity of a speaker and the characteristics of his/her voice and thus make it recognizable by others. The pitch contour, the rate of speech and the duration of the pauses are three of them [12]. However, as stated in [1], the two primary features for speaker identification are the overall shape of the spectral envelope along with the fundamental frequency. Voice conversion is commonly based on fundamental frequency normalization in order to solely deal with the timbre. Thus the basic work for voice conversion is focused on the conversion of the whole spectral envelope assumed to contained the timbre

information, without extracting acoustic features.

In addition, the conversion is based on a statistical model, the Gaussian Mixture Model. A parametric GMM is used to model the source speaker timbral space, as a continuous probabilistic density. The transformation function can be considered as a time-continuous function that is applied on the source data on a frame-by-frame basis, in order to perform the envelope-based conversion.

The main methodology and core of the VCF and the ITF remain the same, but the framework has undergone many modifications in order to be able to adapt and perform in the case of musical instruments. The modifications and additions are explained in detail in 4.4.

2.2 Stages of a VC system

Most existing VC systems have two distinct stages:

- The training stage, where a predefined database of source and target speech samples are analyzed and processed. The result of this stage is a trained statistical model, which can be used to extract a source to target mapping, namely the transformation function of our system. We will refer to the total of the audio forming the database for training as the training set.
- The transformation stage, where the source data is transformed according to the transformation function calculated in the previous step. The database containing audio that will be used for evaluation will be referred to as evaluation set.

We will be looking at these stages in more detail in chapter 4 when studying the corresponding section of our system.

2.3 Spectral envelope modeling

Since our system's success is partly based on the used envelope representation, a fast method to obtain an accurate envelope is necessary. Instead of using a simple LPC-based estimation, the implemented system incorporates a wide-band analysis [13] to extract harmonic information and then uses an all-pole (autoregressive) model to extract an improved envelope estimation. This method is known as WB-AR and in our case, Line Spectral Frequencies (LSFs) are used to represent the all-pole model that is given as input to our system. A further improved method for envelope estimation, based on the concept of "true envelope" estimation can be found in [3] and is already being used for voice conversion in the MTG. However, this technique has not been incorporated in our system as it is slightly more costly than the aforementioned one.

2.4 Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs)

A Gaussian mixture model is a specific case of a probabilistic mixture model. In such a model, the probability distribution of a variable x is represented as a weighted sum or mixture of N components that are usually called clusters or classes. When dealing with a Gaussian mixture model, the components are Gaussian distributions with the following probability distribution:

$$P_{GMM}(x; \alpha, \mu, \Sigma) = \sum_{q=1}^Q \alpha_q N(x; \mu_q, \Sigma_q), \sum_{q=1}^Q \alpha_q = 1, \alpha_q \geq 0 \quad (2.1)$$

where α_q stands for the prior probabilities of x generated by the component q and $N(x; \mu_q, \Sigma_q)$ the n -dimensional normal distribution with mean vector μ and covariance matrix Σ given by:

$$N(x; \mu, \Sigma) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{n/2} \sqrt{|\Sigma|}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}(x - \mu)^T \Sigma^{-1} (x - \mu)\right) \quad (2.2)$$

The conditional probability of a GMM class q given x is derived by direct application of Bayes' rule

$$p(c_q|x) = \frac{\alpha_q N(x; \mu_q, \Sigma_q)}{\sum_{p=1}^Q \alpha_p N(x; \mu_p, \Sigma_p)} \quad (2.3)$$

In order to estimate the maximum likelihood parameters of the GMM, α, μ, Σ , the iterative algorithm of Expectation-Maximization is used [17]. The method is identical to the one described in [2] and [1]. However, the EM algorithm is guaranteed to converge toward a stable maximum. This maximum however is not guaranteed to be the overall maximum. In this sense, the initialization of the parameters for the EM plays a crucial role in its stability, convergence and also in the final estimate. The vector quantization technique is used for the initialization of the algorithm.

For a GMM $(\alpha_q, \mu_q, \Sigma_q, i = 1, \dots, m)$, and with source vectors $\{x_t, t = 1, \dots, n\}$, the conversion function $F(x)$ for an input x_t and output y_t is defined as:

$$\hat{y} = F(x_t) = \sum_{q=1}^Q [W_q x + b_q] p(c_q|x_t) \quad (2.4)$$

where W is the transformation matrix and b_q is a bias vector of class q defined as:

$$W_q = \Sigma_q^{YX} (\Sigma_q^{XX})^{-1} \quad (2.5)$$

and

$$b_q = \mu_q^Y - \Sigma_q^{YX} (\Sigma_q^{XX})^{-1} \mu_q^X \quad (2.6)$$

More details on the mathematical background of the GMM-based method are beyond the scope of this thesis and can be found in [14] and [2].

2.5 GMM usage in conversion and morphing

A sound morphing framework based on GMMs has been presented and evaluated in [4]. In that case, the GMM was used to build the acoustic model of the source sound and to formulate the set of the conversion functions. The experiments presented showed that the method was effective in performing spectral transformations while preserving the time evolution of the source sound.

In [5] a similar probabilistic system that took advantage of spectral analysis of natural sound recordings, Cluster-Weighted Modeling (CWM) was incorporated in order to perform perceptually meaningful acoustic timbre synthesis for continuously-pitched acoustic instruments, in their case, the violin, giving encouraging results.

2.6 GMM usage in instrument classification

In the bibliography there appear several successful attempts to use GMMs in instrument discrimination and classification. While positive results in classification does not necessarily mean that GMMs can perform well in the field on transformation. However it is a first step that highlights the capability of GMMs in discriminating between different characteristics of instruments by using different spectral representations such as LPC, MFCC, etc.

In [7], an extensive study is being conducted on the performance of GMMs in instrument classification. An eight-instrument (bagpipes, clarinet, flute, harpsichord, organ, piano, trombone and violin) classifier is proposed and its performance is compared to that of the Support Vector Machines, ranking 7% higher in error rate. Also the set consisting of mel cepstral features is promoted as the one giving the lowest error rate.

In [8] we can find a comparative approach for a set of instruments comprising of clean electric guitar, distorted electric guitar, drums, piano and bass. Here emphasis is given to the input representation that is fed into the GMM.

The performance of the GMM was again evaluated using different spectral rep-

representations as LPC, MFCCs and sinusoidal-modeling as instruments features. The best results were obtained when we using a combined set of MFCCs and LPCs together as features, with three Gaussians in the mixture model, resulting in classification accuracy of 90.18%.

Chapter 3

Towards instrument timbre conversion

This novel approach of using an envelope-based, statistical method for instrument timbre transformation is based on the hypothesis of the possibility of transformation of the source spectral envelope (one representation for it, in our case LSF) into a target spectral envelope. The use of GMMs or similar probabilistic methods has been applied with success in the past for morphing [4], further encouraging us to proceed towards this direction.

3.1 Motivation

Using the method presented in 2.3, we are provided with an accurate representation of the spectral envelope. Using GMMs we are enabled to model this difference in a statistical fashion and extract a function to transform the spectral envelope of a given input signal. In the case of voice, which is a relatively band-limited signal the efficiency of this transformation have been proved to be adequate. However, when dealing with musical instruments we have to carefully study the characteristics of each instrument, in terms of the form of the spectral envelope as well as the combined characteristics of any proposed source-target pair.

As mentioned in the introduction, we had defined our initial set of instruments to contain the electric guitar, the acoustic guitar and a brass instrument, in our case

Figure 3.1: Clarinet vs. Alto Saxophone spectral envelopes (averaged for all frames of a single note), 1st octave

the alto saxophone. The guitar however, being a percussive/plucked instrument, introduces characteristics such as fast attacks and steep onsets that are harder to model with the a system that is based on the transformation of the stationary information of a signal and demands special attention. For that reason, the guitar was not a good candidate for the preliminary tests of our model.

In order to verify the functionality and usefulness of the conversion framework, we decided to proceed with an initial conversion between two wind instruments, which have in general smoother attacks and bigger attack times, but above all which envelope information is stationary. After making some tests with alto saxophone, soprano saxophone and clarinet we defined the initial process to be an alto-to-

Figure 3.2: Clarinet vs. Alto Saxophone spectral envelopes (averaged for all frames of a single note), 2nd octave

soprano sax transformation and our instrument set to consist of the pair: {alto saxophone, soprano saxophone}. This choice was due to the fact that they are two instruments of the same family and from the tests we conducted for different octaves and for distinct dynamics, they seemed to have similar harmonic structure and envelope behavior, as well as visible envelope differences. This way it is more straightforward to verify the validity of our proposal.

The clarinet on the other hand has only odd harmonics, something that heavily affects the form of the spectral envelope. Also the connection (or the lack of) and mapping of the odd-even harmonics was likely to degrade the performance of the system. For that reasons, the clarinet did not serve for the preliminary tests. The initial comparisons that refrained us from using this pair can be seen in figures 3.1 and 3.2. Experiments with clarinet or instruments with similar harmonic structure

can be conducted in the future.

Figure 3.3: Clarinet vs. Alto Saxophone Spectrum

A leading factor to encourage the success of the system would be the detection of some identifiable form/shape of the envelopes, when studying different octaves and dynamics (piano, mezzo, forte in our case). In the previous case, there is no such obvious tendency that makes it an inappropriate first trial set. We can also observe a drastic difference in the form of the two envelopes, since the slope of the clarinet envelope is steeper and diminishes fast, while strong peaks can be seen at

Figure 3.4: The case of harmonic inefficiency for transformation with the existing GMM framework. The clarinet (blue) is more band-limited than the saxophone (green) and most of the harmonic content is contained in LF (thus the characterization 'poor in content'). In that case special techniques including the envelope residual might improve the performance

the odd harmonics. On the other hand the alto saxophone seems to diminish slower, having strong harmonic content even in high frequencies.

The envelope results however were a lot more promising in the case of the alto and soprano saxophones. As it can be seen in figure 3.5, there is a coherent tendency between the two instruments in both octaves. Even though the representation used in this case comes from a rough LPC estimation, the overall tendency can be identified. These preliminary tests lead us to proceed with the instrument pair {alto

Figure 3.5: Alto vs. Soprano saxophone envelope comparison, 2 octaves

saxophone, soprano saxophone}.

It is worth noting that the specific pair is a good-case scenario. This does not mean that the ITF only addresses a subset of cases. However in more elaborate cases, where we have to deal with difficult harmonic/envelope matching, one might need to consider instrument-specific solutions and techniques like the residual envelope proposed in 6.2.1. One of these cases is the aforementioned case of the *clarinet2alto* transformation, which problems can be seen in figure 3.4.

3.2 Notes and phonemes

When working with vocal data, the notion of phonemes is introduced. In human phonology, a phoneme (meaning in Greek “an uttered sound”) is the smallest segmental unit of sound which is used to form meaningful contrasts between utterances. Phonemes generally carry no semantic content themselves, nor are they physical segments, but rather the equivalence class of such segments. A big part of the functionality of the VCF was based on phonemes, them being the cornerstone of speech.

However, when it comes to music, the notion of phoneme doesn’t have any physical substance. Instead notes take its place. This way, solely for processing reasons we have defined a correspondence between note and a phoneme in the implementation. This was done to facilitate the implementation and porting from the VC framework, since the data alignment that used to be done for the corresponding phonemes, in our case will be carried out for the corresponding notes. The latter is based on the hypothesis that while in voice, the mapping for the timbre conversion is based on phoneme correspondence, in instruments this timbral mapping is equivalent to the notes played. Furthermore, this distinction does not only include a mapping of the base notes, but also a distinction between their octaves, using the scientific music notation (C2 and C3 for two C notes in different octaves) to label them. The note alignment step is further described in section 4.2.

3.3 Instrument dependency

Each instrument has its proper characteristics. The variation of those characteristics can be considered in many levels, such as that of harmonic structure (harmonics, envelope, fundamental frequency), that of character (color, timbre) or that of linearity (linear or non-linear behavior and dynamics), among others. In the context of this thesis we conduct a specific preliminary experiment to test the capacity of our framework to perform in one specifically defined scenario, that we describe further

on.

As mentioned before, the instrument set has been chosen to contain similar instruments (same family and behavior) and aim to the transformation of their timbral characteristics. In order to address a different or more generic set, one must take into account the special nuances of each instrument and carefully select the quantity and quality of data to include in the training set in order to enable the system to perform.

3.4 Database instrument characteristics

The instrument-specific characteristics have to be considered in a transformation framework. Our instruments of interest, namely the alto and the soprano saxophone, are presented in the first appendix (section 6.2) for completeness as a reference with respect to their general and harmonic characteristics, their pitch range as well as their sound production mechanism.

Chapter 4

Proposed system

In this chapter we explain in detail the concept, the steps and the details of our system. We will start by giving a generic overview of the data flow, which is similar to the one of the VC presented in chapter 2, but with some modifications. These implementation-specific modifications are presented in detail in the following sections. The system will be referred to as Instrument Transformation Framework (ITF).

4.1 System overview

In this section we present both the training and the evaluation stage of the ITF in detail. Figure 4.1 depicts an overview of the system.

Training Stage The training stage is an offline pre-process during which, a large volume of data which correspond to the training set is analyzed. The audio is preprocessed as described in detail in 4.2 and the output of our training stage is a trained GMM model. From this model, the transformation function that serves for the frame-based stage of the transformation is derived. More in-depth explanation of the steps of the training can be found in section 4.2.

Transformation Stage During the analysis stage of the transformation, the source audio signal is processed and its envelope and harmonic structure are extracted. The envelope is represented with the help of LSF (described in section

Figure 4.1: An overview of the ITF: Training and evaluation stages

2.3), in the same way as in the training stage. During the synthesis, the source LSFs are transformed using the transformation function and, with the help of a phase-locked vocoder, we obtain the output audio signal. The process is carried out in a frame-by-frame fashion, therefore it is appropriate for a real-time implementation. More details on the transformation stage and the real-time implementation can be found in sections 4.3 and 6.2.2 respectively.

4.2 Training stage

For our tests, we incorporated the use of one of the most extensive and complete instrument databases available, the RWC database ([21]). This database contains real-life recordings of quality instruments, playing an ascending series of notes that cover the whole pitch range of each respective instrument. In our training set we initially included six files containing the recordings of an alto and a soprano saxophone in 2 different octaves, both played at 3 different dynamics.

To conclude to the samples used we had to choose from variety available in the database. Three different brands of saxophones were available, each with a different musician performing in each recording. What's more, several styles of playing were included, so we had to choose the most appropriate subsets in order to obtain satisfying results.

The playing styles available were the normal style (regular blowing technique), vibrato style, blow style, staccato style as well as an extra style containing high-pitched harmonics that results from a change in the blowing type.

For this work, we have used the recordings of a Yamaha alto saxophone played in both normal and vibrato style, with the possibility of including staccato samples. These weren't included as in order to record these samples, the player has to blow pretty strong, thus producing saturation in the harmonic excitation of the instrument 6.2.

We arranged the training set to be coherent with respect to the notes played so that we can have a more supervisory overview of the correspondence between the training files. To the aforementioned six files, we added six extra files containing similar recordings but with vibrato, to measure how our system corresponds to the addition of vibrato samples in the training.

More details on the size and qualities of the different training sets can be found in table 4.1.

TS title	TS details	TS Size
Training Set 1 [TS1]	All dynamics, 2 Octaves, Normal mode blowing	27.318 vectors
Training Set 2 [TS2]	TS1 + Partial Vibrato (2 Octaves, 1 Dynamic)	37.403 vectors
Training Set 3 [TS3]	TS1 + Full Vibrato (2 Octaves, 3 Dynamics)	74.517 vectors
Training Set 4 [TS4]	TS3 + RMS addition	74.517 vectors

Table 4.1: Training Set Details

Training Steps

1. Load the instrument database: During this step, the audio files are loaded into the database, analyzed and labeled. The analysis consists of frame-based processing, fundamental frequency estimation, harmonic analysis (modeling and storing of the harmonic peaks to be used in the envelope calculation) and note labeling. This stage consists of two parts, one for the source instrument (alto saxophone) and one for the target (soprano saxophone). It is worth noting that for a real-time implementation, we can avoid the fundamental frequency estimation and replace it with an estimation of the envelope.
2. Estimate time correspondence based on the note segmentation: In this section the note alignment is performed. Stable parts of each detected note are time-aligned between the source and target database.
3. Build a structure with time-aligned joint source-target data: During this step, a common structure containing the time-aligned data of source and target is created to be used in the GMM training.
4. Gaussian Mixture Model for Linear Regression training: In this final step, the GMM is trained using the above structures containing all the necessary information extracted from the database.

Here, it is worth noting that in voice conversion, the training set is assumed to cover the whole timbre space of the speakers. We can therefore expect that

the model is capable of dealing with any possible given input. This assumption is valid on speech signals if the training set contains a number of repetitions of all the phonemes. However, in instrument transformation this is not always true as in many cases the pitch range of the instruments is not identical so there are notes and pitches that can not be aligned. In these cases we have to concentrate on the overlapping pitches and base the training on them, verifying to what extent this limitation can produce acceptable results.

4.3 Transformation stage

During this stage, the input audio is analyzed, exactly the same way as the training samples were analyzed and is processed by the pre-trained transformation function stemming from the trained GMM model. The parameters of the transformation consist of the following:

- **envModel** is the model of the envelope to be used. Can be either a mel-frequency or linear-frequency based AR model represented by LSF coefficients.
- **envOrder** is the order of the LSF used. More details on that can be found in section 4.4.3.
- **gmmSize** is the size of the model that is used for the transformation.
- **dataSize** is the limit (if applies) of the data to be transformed. Data beyond that limit are left intact.
- **maxClusteringDim** is the clustering to be performed. This shows the percentage of coefficients of the LSF vector that is actually taken into account. More details on that can be found in section 4.4.3.

The transformation function is represented as an equalization that is applied for each frame. After the transformation of the LSF coefficients, synthesis follows

in order to obtain the final output audio signal. Synthesis is carried out using a phase-locked vocoder as mentioned in section 4.1.

4.4 Implementation and architecture of the ITF

As mentioned in 2, the original VC framework, being designed for use with vocal data, was based on many assumptions that didn't apply in the case of instruments. For that reason, it had to be adapted and enriched so that successful and most importantly, meaningful processing could be carried out.

4.4.1 File segmentation

Initially, a function processes each file in the training and the evaluation set and segments it in regions depending on the time-domain envelope. This results in the automatic segmentation of the notes in each file and the creation of two "pointer vectors", containing the start (S vector) and end (E vector) points to each detected note.

4.4.2 Note alignment

As explained in section 3.2, we took advantage of the notion of phonemes and along these guidelines, we implemented a function that processes the pre-trimmed audio and using the fundamental frequency detection results for each frame calculates the existing notes within the boundaries S and E obtained during the segmentation. Then it assigns a label containing the note and its time limits and returns a structure containing all the above to further processing. The vector containing the notes replaces the corresponding phoneme vector.

4.4.3 LSF dimension and trimming

The harmonic representation used to extract the spectral envelopes consists of the spectral peaks of the detected harmonics. For our experiments, we use the method

described in section 2.3 to represent an all-pole model.

One can choose to take into consideration the information contained at the spectral peaks in its entirety or can choose to ignore some of them. The reason to do that is that, for example, trimming the last LSF coefficients corresponds to trimming out the highest areas of the spectrum that contain the highest frequencies. This can be useful depending of the kind of signal we want to process, as usually the information contained there is mostly noise.

The LSF dimension is also an issue as in some cases, especially in higher octaves when analyzing music, the frequency points extracted from harmonic analysis set an upper bound to the dimension of the LSF that can be used. In the current implementation we can not infinitely increase the dimensions of the LSF as we don't have enough spectral peak points that correspond. However, if higher LSF dimensions is necessary, oversampling and interpolation of the given harmonic analysis can be performed to increase the number of the available spectral points.

In our tests, the LSF dimension that was found to be appropriate in the sense of delivering acceptable results and, at the same time, satisfying the aforementioned criteria based on the number of harmonic peaks, was 30. So the majority of the tests and results presented in this work are done with an LSF vector of dimension equal to 30.

4.5 Issues and challenges

In the following section we review the most important issues and challenges that have arisen during this work till now. Part of this section is closely related to section 6.2, assigning the current problematic issues and aspects of the ITF as work for the future.

4.5.1 ITF data preprocessing

One of the most challenging problems we encountered during this work is the sufficient modeling of the non-stationary parts of the processed signals, since the note

labeling and definition of the time boundaries of the notes in our algorithm are based on the f_0 detection. Knowing that the training set is monophonic and is a sequence of notes ascending in pitch, we can set the boundaries to each note starting from any given point (from the onset and further on) and ending to any given point (before the end of the offset or even including the whole offset). Thus an important drawback of the implemented system is the high emphasis given on the harmonic and stationary fragments of the sound. This being said, one can foresee that the performance of the ITF will be more satisfactory in harmonic and more stable parts and more problematic in the transitions, onsets, offsets and generally unstable, non-stationary parts.

The f_0 detection obviously has irregular behavior in these non-stationary parts (onsets, offsets) and thus it requires special manipulation. As a first approach we chose to ignore (trim out) a percentage of these parts and consider as valid data only the stationary parts of the audio. By doing that, we can evaluate the performance of the system for stationary parts, but as we can listen to the audio results there are glitches at exactly these parts, as the system is undertrained and doesn't now have explicit knowledge as to how to treat them.

4.5.2 Frame RMS and f_0 addition

The GMM vectors that are used as inputs to the system (for both training and evaluation) contain the LSF coefficients representing the envelope of each frame. However, taking into account that in the case of musical instruments, we have to deal with advanced features as dynamics, vibrato techniques, etc., we consider two extra elements that can be taken advantage of, in order to further improve the performance of the system.

The first is to include in database of features of the training set the room mean square (RMS) energy of each frame. The second one is to include an element contained the normalized fundamental frequency, further enriching the information that will be taken into account for the cluster differentiation.

Preliminary tests we conducted shows a decrease in the average error rate when incorporating these two features. More tests have been assigned as future work to verify the exact benefit from this modification, before it's completely incorporated in the framework. However, one important drawback for the inclusion of the f_0 , is the introduction of undesired latency in a real time situation. Preliminary results for the effect of the incorporation of the RMS in the feature vector can be seen in figure 5.3

Chapter 5

Results and Evaluation

In this chapter we present the results we have extracted during this work. We present three distinct types of results, error rate evaluation (source-target envelopes), clustering selection performance/stability and finally perceptual, auditory results.

5.1 Average error rate

We tested our system for the following range of GMM sizes: $\{2, 4, 6, 8, 16\}$ and for two distinct cases. In the first case we included the evaluation set (ES) in the training set (TS) and the results were the expected ones, that is for increasing GMM size, the average error, which corresponds to an averaged spectral distortion in the envelopes, dropped. When excluding the evaluation set from the training set, we obtained a parabolic-type graph which was also to be expected. Both curves can be seen in figure 5.1. The second curve was also to be expected and figure 5.1 basically provides us with the following valuable pieces of information:

- The model has a minimum error for GMM size equal to four for a small training set. When our GMM size is smaller than that, the error rises as the model does not have sufficient size to take advantage of the amount of data in the training set.
- When rising above the minimum the amount of training data is not sufficient to take advantage of the GMM model size, so the error rises.

Figure 5.1: Average error for various GMM sizes and for both cases when evaluation set is included and excluded from the training set. ES /TS size: 4270 / 27318 vectors.

- The fact that the curve that corresponds to the case when we didn't include the evaluation set in the training has one minimum is encouraging as it verifies that our model is learning correctly from the training set. The motivation for our experiment is thus enforced.
- The GMM size that corresponds to the minimum error is reasonably low. This is due to the fact that we are using a rather small and incomplete training set. Incorporating more data into the training set helps rise this limit.

Figure 5.2: Average error for the normal TS and for extended TS with vibrato samples added. ES /TS size: 4270 / 37403 vectors.

- As seen in figure 5.2, the extension of the TS to TS2, with the addition of partial vibrato samples maintains the error curve tendency but drops the overall error, suggesting that vibrato samples contribute positively to the quality of the TS.
- When further extending the TS (TS3) by including a large number of extra samples (the whole vibrato database), the curve is moved to the right, having a minimum value for GMM complexity equal to 8. This is very positive as it depicts how our model is taking advantage of the extra data and because of

Figure 5.3: Average error for all the training sets, including the error when RMS feature is used. RMS ES /TS size: 4270 / 74517 vectors.

that improves its performance for bigger GMM sizes. Results in figure 5.3.

- When adding a field containing the normalized RMS energy of each frame in the feature vectors used for training, the error drops even further, even though not significantly. This could be due to the selected normalization type, and its coherence with the LSF range. Results in figure 5.3.

5.2 Saxophone pattern tendency

In this section we present a fundamental part of our research, demonstrating the connection of the spectral envelope curves with the ranges of notes. When dealing with voice, the connection of a phoneme and a specific spectral envelope curve enables us to model the timbre features by a GMM.

In our case however, it has been impossible to find a specific pattern of change in the spectral envelope between each and every one of the single notes of the training set. In fact, many notes seemed similar in terms of spectral envelope, while others differed. However, observing the spectral envelopes of all the notes in our set, there seemed to be some characteristics that led us to the following results and conclusions, regarding the validity of the envelope-based technique for our scenario:

- The envelope does not explicitly change for each note, making it difficult to extract safe conclusions on whether the method we are using is meaningful for the transformation.
- If that were true, and there was indeed no connection, our system would be inappropriate for instrument conversion along the aforementioned lines. The preliminary sound results that were encouraging could have been due to some kind of general equalization that the system performs in average, not making real use of the gmm clusters available.
- There are indeed some groups of notes that show very similar envelopes among them. When changing groups of notes the envelope drastically changes. For example in the first used octave, in both alto and soprano, the group {G#3 - E3} consisting of 9 notes seemed to have a common shaped envelope, while after that the envelope changed but remained stable for the while group within the range {F3 - C4}.
- Although these changes at first seemed random, observing the physiology and the register of the saxophone we observed the connection of the grouping of

the envelopes with the physical area of the saxophone that is used to play each note. Part of this can be seen in figure 5.4, where the note $G\sharp$ in the key of saxophone (Bb .) is the first one that uses the upper part of the register (the cross-like, four-piece key). This note transposed into piano notation is the aforementioned F . We can find several such connections.

- However, due to the complex structure and construction of the saxophone, it's hard to extract and even demonstrate all the connections in detail, as it would require a special study that is beyond the scope of this work. In any case, observing these preliminary observations encouraged us proceed with a more extensive testing that confirmed our hypothesis, as presented in section 5.3.

The figure displays two musical staves with corresponding fingering diagrams for an alto saxophone. The top staff is in G major (one sharp) and the bottom staff is in F major (one flat). The top staff has a label "octave (thumb) key" with an arrow pointing to the first note. The bottom staff has a label "B-flat fingerings" and "1 and 1 bis side" below it. Each note on the staff is accompanied by a diagram of the saxophone keys and finger positions.

Figure 5.4: Alto saxophone fingering index, note-position correspondence

5.3 Clustering

In this section we take a look at the internal behavior of the system in terms of cluster selection. As we have seen, during the training stage the system is selecting the

Figure 5.5: Source envelopes of the trained model *soprano2alto*, each corresponding to one cluster (GMM=8)

dominant envelope patterns and assigns each one to each cluster. Then during the transformation, the function is selected as a probabilistic weighted sum of clusters. In practice, there is usually a cluster with probability closer of equal to one, so the final transformation is performed based on one cluster for each frame.

However, we first checked the meaning of the clustering, by comparing the envelopes selected to be modeled by our system and their selection during the process. In figures 5.5 and 5.7 we can observe that for a GMM of size 8, the envelopes vary significantly, leading us to believe that the system is correctly trained and is indeed

Figure 5.6: Target envelopes of the trained model *soprano2alto*, each corresponding to one cluster (GMM=8)

modeling spectral envelope differences. This is especially obvious in figure 5.7 where the difference between source and target envelopes is depicted. The curves vary and are not near zero, showing significant differences between the various modeled envelopes.

Following that analysis, we had to look at the cluster selection in the transformation process and how the selection is taking place during the evolution of our signal in time. As we see in figure 5.8 and 5.9 there is a pattern in the selection of clusters and more than one clusters are used. In the contrary case we would be dealing with equalization and misuse of the system's capabilities.

Figure 5.7: Difference of the envelopes for all the clusters, soprano2alto (GMM=8)

5.3.1 Alto2Soprano

In the first scenario, the transformation alto2soprano gave us good perceptual results, even for small GMM sizes, that is using only four clusters. Looking at the clusters we observed that two or even three of them (depending on the training set) were similar. This was discouraging at first, as could show that the process corresponds to some kind of generic equalization. However, the perceptual evaluation of the audio results was very encouraging. By studying the quality of the source and target sounds further, it results that an alto2soprano transformation is more accessible due to the “colors” of the instruments (and of the specific samples we

Figure 5.8: Cluster selection for alto2soprano transformation, 4 clusters, 1st octave transformation. Top: Signal, time domain. Middle: Cluster conditional probability. Bottom: Final cluster selection

used). More specifically, the alto has a brighter, more aggressive sound while the soprano is smoother with a kind of “muffled” high end. The cluster selection along the frame evolution showed us stable parts of the signal, where the same cluster was selected.

5.3.2 Soprano2Alto

When studying the inverse transformation scenario, we were able to extract some more interesting results. This was due to the nature of the instruments. As mentioned in section 5.3.1, the alto2soprano transformation could be generally modeled as a form of equalization. However, the soprano2alto scenario would be a lot harder

Figure 5.9: Cluster selection for alto2soprano transformation, 6 clusters, 1st octave transformation. Top: Signal, time domain. Middle: Cluster conditional probability. Bottom: Final cluster selection

if not impossible to implement, as there are many details in the envelope that would have to be reconstructed from a noisy spectral region.

So, observing the results, especially in figures 5.10 and 5.10 depicting the cluster selection for the the transformation of the first and second octave respectively, we confirm that the selection changes with as notes change. More precisely, we can see that for the first 5+3 notes ($\{1,2,3,4,5,7,8,9\}$) cluster 3 is selected. Cluster 7 is selected for the intermediate note 6. This is a special case in the training of the system as the corresponding envelopes for clusters 3 and 7 are very similar and thus almost interchangeable as it can be seen by their corresponding probabilities, in the middle subfigure of figure 5.10. The tendency changed starting at the 10th note

Figure 5.10: Cluster selection for soprano2alto transformation, 8 clusters, 1st octave transformation. Top: Signal, time domain. Middle: Cluster conditional probability. Bottom: Final cluster selection

up to the 16th, in the middle of the first octave, with the choice of cluster 5. The same correspondence (first nine notes, etc.) was observed when studying different dynamics. In that case the pattern was also followed. The points of differentiation in our case are connected to the physical register of the saxophone, as explained in section 5.2. These results were another confirmation that the system successfully makes use of the available cluster range.

Figure 5.11: Signal and cluster selection for soprano2alto transformation, 8 clusters, 2nd octave transformation

5.4 Perceptual evaluation of audio

The initial listening tests have been proven quite successful, as the general tendency and characteristics of the timbre of the soprano saxophone can be heard and confirmed in the straight case. The resulting sounds have the same temporal envelope as the source ones, which means that the ITF manages to maintain the time domain characteristics of the input signal while altering the timbre properly. We have noticed several issues:

- **Successfully transformed timbral characteristics:** In most parts, clustering was stable and the timbre of the transformed sound was very close to

the target timbre. Even in cases of random saxophone samples that were real-life phrases, without note patterns and distinct distances between the notes, the transformation was successful and the timbre instantly recognizable.

- **Transitions and non-stationarity:** One of the problematic parts have proven to be the onsets of the notes, as expected. However, the model seemed to be using a combination of cluster to try and model these non-stationary parts, with some success. The results were not excellent, as the system was not originally thought to model these parts, but the auditory results showed us that these parts were also transformed properly for most of the cases, giving us a convincing and coherent sound results.
- **Energy bursts caused by asymmetric switching between the GMM clusters:** We observed in the results (acoustically and inspecting the output waveforms) that the transformations results in the appearance of sudden inharmonic energy bursts. This is a first priority issue that has to be addressed and is probably due to unstable allocation and selection of cluster correspondence. We can also observe that in the figures of section 5.3.
- **Overall amplitude amplification and clipping:** Another results of the transformation is the amplification of the output pulses, as a consequence of elevated target envelope curves. This can be resolved by normalizing the input pulses or by limiting the transformation parameters.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

6.1 Conclusions

In this work we addressed the issue of timbral instrument transformation. To achieve that, we emphasized on the hypothesis that most relevant timbre information is contained in the spectral envelope of a musical signal. The spectral envelope was modeled using an all-pole model and represented using LSFs. A statistical method called Gaussian mixture model was used to model the differentiations in the spectral envelopes, and through that, the final transformation function was extracted. The original framework was originally thought and proposed for voice processing and conversion which made it inappropriate for direct application on recorded audio from musical instruments. For that reasons several modifications were made, in order to make it appropriate for use with instruments. The scenario we presented, comprised of the timbre transformation of an alto saxophone into a soprano saxophone and vice-versa using the aforementioned method. The results, in terms of theoretical error as well as in terms of perceptual performance were satisfactory and very promising:

After a series of adaptations, our framework delivered some satisfactory first results:

- The obtained average error curves obtained demonstrated that meaningful training of this kind of system with instrumental data is possible.

- The system seems to be properly taking advantage of the training data, assigning meaningfully selected clusters and performing non-equalization like transformation in the cases where this is necessary. This was demonstrated in section 5.3.
- The preliminary perceptual auditory results were positive, convincing and encouraging, as mentioned in section 5.4. The timbre of the transformed output sound is close to that of the target instrument and the characteristics of the input (time evolution of the signal, some dynamics, temporal envelope) are maintained as mentioned in chapter 5.

6.2 Future work

The present work has given several interesting and promising results, as presented in the previous chapter. Many of them can be extended and can serve for future research. In this section, we present some of the main points that have to be addressed in the future as refinements or extensions to this work.

- **Improving the training set:** The performance of the ITF heavily depends on the quality and size of the training set. However it is hard to come across well-organized, generalized and appropriate data (especially since we are looking into saxophone transformation). In this sense, constant extension of the database is a continuous goal.
- **Discrimination based on frame RMS energy and fundamental frequency as described in section 4.5.2.** Preliminary work on the use of RMS has been presented, however more extensive experiments are needed in order to formally present the benefits made available by this method.
- **Non-linear instrument behavior:** Another issue that arises is the behavior of the ITF when the input signal does not have linear characteristics. For example when the input saxophone signal is a results of heavy blowing and

the instrument functions in saturation. Along with that, there are many issues that arise such as gesture handling and instrument-specific problems that have to be taken into account. However this is a very complex matter that is hard to be dealt within the time frame of the present thesis.

- **Residual envelope transformation:** This technique can be an important addition to the system, more details can be found in section 6.2.1.
- **Real time implementation:** As explained, the frame-by-frame basis of the system is encouraging towards a real-time implementation. More details can be found in section 6.2.2.

6.2.1 Residual envelope transformation

As mentioned in chapter 3, there are cases where the envelope matching process can prove an extremely complicated goal, with the given framework. When the source and target envelopes are radically different, or one of the two (or both) have special characteristics (e.g. odd harmonics), the conversion of the envelope tendency is not enough to capture large part of the harmonic content. In these cases the system will suffer losses in details as the peaks corresponding to partials will be smoothed out, resulting in the aforementioned loss of detail and thus clarity.

For that reason, the idea of spectral residual is introduced. This method suggests that during the training, along with the source and target envelope representations, the residual (their difference) is taken into account. This residual is included in the model and later on added to each target component that will be used in the transformation and reconstruction. This way, the spectral envelopes that correspond to the components contain a representation of the envelope plus a residual which renders the envelope approximation a lot more detailed and thus, enables better performance in terms of quality.

6.2.2 Real-Time implementation (VST)

Part of this work and our motivation originated by the implementation of parts of the system in C++ for real time processing. This was encouraged by the fact that the presented framework work on a frame-by-frame processing basis.

The voice conversion framework is partially implemented in Matlab and partially implemented in C++. At the moment of the writing of this thesis, the Matlab code is used for both offline training and conversion as it contains many details still missing from the C++ code. However, the core part of the conversion has been implemented and is already functioning in C++ for voice.

The weakest point that creates most of the inconveniences is located in the training stage details and the training set, so most of the effort was focused on improving the offline training of the system, as discussed previously. The training process, being a non-critical process in terms of time, can be carried out using Matlab. Future work can address the adjustment and adaptation of the existing real-time framework for voice, in order for it to serve in the case of musical instruments, and form part of the ITF.

Appendix A: Saxophone bibliographical reference

This appendix is presented here solely for completeness and reference, as it contains descriptions concerning the two main instruments that were used in this work. Other than their overall characteristics, more specific harmonic structure characteristics, pitch range charts as well as information concerning the linearity and non-linearity of the alto and soprano saxophone are presented. Full credit for this information is given to [22].

.1 Overview

Both the alto and the soprano saxophone are members of the saxophone family of woodwind instruments invented by the Belgian instrument designer Adolphe Sax. The saxophone family consists, as generally accepted, (from smallest to largest) of the sopranino, soprano, alto, tenor, baritone, bass, and contrabass saxophones. Benedikt Eppelsheim has constructed a new “Soprillo” saxophone, which sounds an octave above the soprano.

The saxophone player provides a flow of air at a pressure above that of the atmosphere (technically, a few kPa or a few percent of an atmosphere. This is the source of power input to the instrument, but it is a source of continuous rather than vibratory power. In the saxophone, the reed acts like an oscillating valve (technically, a control oscillator). The reed, in cooperation with the resonances in the air in the instrument, produces an oscillating component of both flow and pressure. Once the air in the saxophone is vibrating, some of the energy is radiated as sound out of the bell and any open holes. A much greater amount of energy is lost as a sort of friction (viscous loss) with the wall. In a sustained note, this energy is replaced by energy put in by the player. The column of air in the saxophone vibrates much more easily at some frequencies than at others (i.e. it resonates at certain frequencies). These resonances largely determine the playing frequency and thus the pitch, and the player in effect chooses the desired resonances by suitable combinations of keys.

Figure 1: Linear/Non-linear behavior of the saxophone depending on blowing dynamics (from [22])

Figure 2: Saxophone pitch range: Alto is in E_b : sounds one sixth lower. Most modern alto saxes can reach a high $F\sharp$. Soprano is in B_b : sounds a major second lower.

In figure 1 we can observe the way the timbre changes when we go from playing softly to loudly. For small variation in pressure and small acoustic flow, the relation between the two is approximately linear, as shown in the diagram below at left. A nearly linear relation gives rise to nearly sinusoidal vibration (i.e. one shaped like a sine wave), which means that the fundamental frequency in the sound spectrum is strong, but that the higher harmonics are weak. This gives rise to a mellow timbre.

As playing loudness increases, the pressure is increased (which moves the operating point to the right) and the range of pressure is also increased. This means

that the (larger) section of the curve used is no longer approximately linear. This produces an asymmetric oscillation. It is no longer a sine wave, so its spectrum has more higher harmonics (centre diagram). The increase of the dynamic level results in a much greater increase of higher harmonics than that of the fundamental.

When the blowing loudness increases even further, the valve closes for part of the part of the cycle when the pressure in the mouthpiece is low due to the standing wave inside the instrument. So the flow is zero for part of the cycle. The resultant waveform is 'clipped' on one side (diagram on the right), and contains even more high harmonics. As well as making the timbre brighter, add more harmonics makes the sound louder as well, because the higher harmonics fall in the frequency range where our hearing is most sensitive.

Figure 3: Two high-range Selmer alto saxophones

.2 Alto saxophone

The alto saxophone is a transposing instrument and reads the treble clef in the key of $E\flat$. A written C for the alto sounds as the concert $E\flat$ a major sixth lower.

The range of the alto saxophone is from concert $D\flat_3$ (the $D\flat$ below middle C) to concert $A\flat_5$ (or A_5 on altos with a high $F\sharp$ key). As with most types of saxophones, the standard written range is $B\flat_3$ to F_6 (or $F\sharp_6$). Above that, the altissimo register begins at $F\sharp$ and extends upwards. The saxophone's altissimo register is more difficult to control than that of other woodwinds and is usually only expected from advanced players.

.3 Soprano saxophone

Figure 4: Two high-range Selmer soprano saxophones

The soprano saxophone was invented in 1840 and is a variety of the saxophone. A transposing instrument pitched in the key of $B\flat$, the soprano saxophone plays an octave above the commonly used tenor saxophone. Some saxophones have addi-

tional keys, allowing them to play an additional F \sharp and G at the top of the range. These extra keys are commonly found on more modern saxophones. Additionally, skilled players can make use of the Altissimo register, which allows them to play even higher. There is also a soprano pitched in C, which is less common and has not been made since around 1940.

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